

LAPAROSCOPIC COLECYSTECTOMY IN LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Abstract

Cirrhosis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. The cirrhotic patient with gallbladder lithiasis has an additional surgical risk. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy appears to be a more effective and safer procedure. The aim of this study is to evaluate the main risks and complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in cirrhotic patients, using the Clavien-Dindo scale, through a retrospective study, including 48 operated patients, in the last 10 years (2015-2024).

The conclusions are:

-patients with Child-Pugh A cirrhosis without portal hypertension have the same indication for elective cholecystectomy as non-cirrhotic ones, but with increased risks; therefore, preoperative management should be adapted to each individual case

-patients with Child-Pugh B cirrhosis or those with portal hypertension require preoperative evaluation and improvement of liver function.

-for patients with Child-Pugh C cirrhosis, with limited life expectancy, surgical interventions should be avoided, seeking non-invasive alternative solutions.

-emergency surgery for acute cholecystitis and the open approach have the highest risk for adverse outcomes.

Keywords: liver cirrhosis, cholecystectomy, laparoscopy

INTRODUCTION

Cirrhosis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Only in Europe, the annual death rate from liver cirrhosis is over 150,000. The prevalence of gallstones in liver cirrhosis is twice as high (about 30%) than in the rest of the population.

The cirrhotic patient has an additional surgical risk. Therefore, cholecystectomy, the surgical treatment of gallbladder lithiasis, is more often followed by complications (perioperative hemorrhages, liver failure, renal failure, postoperative sepsis, wound suppurations). Therefore, the reached consensus was that only

patients with symptomatic gallstones should undergo surgery. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy appears to be a more effective and safer procedure for Child-Pugh class A and B patients, with a shorter duration, lower complication rate, and shorter hospitalization. Things are a little different in the case of Child-Pugh class C cirrhosis.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the main risks and complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in cirrhotic patients, using the Clavien-Dindo scale (table I), through a retrospective study, including 48 operated patients, in the last 10 years (2013-2022).

Table I

CLAVIEN-DINDO CLASSIFICATION OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS
Grade I – any deviation from the natural postoperative evolution, unaccompanied by the need for pharmacological treatment or a surgical, endoscopic or radiological intervention. The therapy included here includes: antiemetics, antipyretics, analgesics, diuretics and electrolytes, physiotherapy. This degree of complications also includes the opening of infected wounds, practiced at the patient's bedside.
Grade II - requires pharmacological treatment with other substances, than those included in the treatment of class I complications, including transfusions and total parenteral nutrition.
Grade III - includes complications, which require a surgical, endoscopic or radiological intervention. III a: intervention that does not require general anesthesia III b: intervention performed under general anesthesia
Grade IV – implies a life-threatening complication (including cerebral hemorrhages, ischemic stroke, sub-arachnoid hemorrhage) IV a: single organ dysfunction (including dialysis) IVb: multiorgan dysfunction
Grade V - death

Material and methods

A retrospective study was carried out, in the last 50 cases of liver cirrhosis, which underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, in the 1st Surgery Clinic of the Braila Clinical Emergency County Hospital, in the period 2013-2022.

The following parameters were evaluated: age, sex, comorbidities, etiology of cirrhosis, number of days of hospitalization (pre- and postoperative), ASA score, degree of urgency, type of cholecystitis (acute or chronic), association of choledocholithiasis, Child-Pugh score, the MELD score, if dialysis was per-

formed, the presence of portal hypertension. Biohumoral markers evaluated: total bilirubin, albumin, fibrinogen, INR, aPTT, GGT, ALT, AST, Na, K, Cl, Ca, creatinine, leukocytes, hemoglobin and platelets.

Results

The mean age was 56 years (46-80). Gender distribution: 26 male (52%), 24 female (49%). Only 13 patients (26%) had no known comorbidities, except for cirrhosis.

The evaluation of the etiology of cirrhosis shows that 20 cases (40%) presented chronic ethanol abuse, 15 cases (30%) presented hepatitis C virus (HCV), 10 cases presented HBV - HCV association (20%), and 5 cases (10%) cryptogenic.

Within the studied group, the ASA score varied between 2 and 4, with most patients 30 (60%) having a 3 score, while the rest were equally divided between ASA 2 and 4, each comprising 10 (20%) patients.

The evaluation of the severity of cirrhosis concluded: 38 patients (75%) Child-Pugh class A, 10 (20%) Child-Pugh class B and only 2 patients (5%) in class C. The mean MELD score was 12 (1 -25).

16 patients (32%) showed signs of portal hypertension, without encephalopathy, of which 9 (18%) with associated ascites, at the time of diagnosis. These ones latter required preoperative treatment for hemodynamic optimization and metabolic disorders. Only one patient was undergoing iterative dialysis.

Only 14 patients (28%) underwent emergency surgery, although 25 (50%) were diagnosed with a form of acute cholecystitis. The minimally invasive approach was preferred in the majority of cases (38 - 75%) with a conversion rate of 10%. Only two patients (4%) had associated choledocholithiasis, and they underwent retrograde endoscopy (ERCP) with preoperative stone extraction.

Evaluation of postoperative complications according to the Dindo-Clavien classification:

0 reinterventions; 35 patients (70%) evolved uneventfully; 12 (23%) developed minor complications (grade I-II), managed conservatively; 2 (4%) needed percutaneous drainage of intra-abdominal collections. 4 patients (2 Child-Pugh B, 2 Child-Pugh C), representing 8% of cases, died. The deaths were recorded in cases with acute cholecystitis and important comorbidities (neoplasia, cardiac decompensation, etc.)

The average preoperative hospital stay of days was 5 days (0-14), and postoperative 7 days (5-21).

Discussions

The vast majority of studies on biliary surgery in cirrhotic patients focus on lithiasic cholecystitis. The incidence of cholelithiasis in cirrhotic patients is twice as high then in those without cirrhosis.

Pathogenic factors cited as responsible for lithogenesis in this group: hemolysis, hypersplenism, decreased concentration of bile acids, metabolic liver failure (leading to increased unconjugated bilirubinemia and gallbladder dysfunction).

Surgery in the cirrhotic patient has always been a delicate subject, with limited indications, due to the increased risk of intraoperative accidents and postopera-

tive complications. The surgical decision for cholecystectomy, in cirrhotic patients, should be made carefully, because of the risks of liver failure and severe bleeding, especially in those with obvious clinical signs of portal hypertension. In addition, biliary surgery in the presence of liver cirrhosis, registers a mortality of 7-15% (according to the present study).

Currently, worldwide, it is considered that the laparoscopic approach for acute cholecystitis, in Child-Pugh class A and B cirrhosis, is preferable, having lower morbidity and mortality rates. For Child-Pugh C cirrhosis, it is recommended to insist on conservative treatment or, if necessary, percutaneous cholecystostomy. Reported conversion rates vary between 4 and 8%, with increased morbidity and mortality risks.

There is a possible correlation between the Child-Pugh scale and the MELD score, for morbidity, (bleeding, wound and intra-abdominal suppuration - all treated conservatively) - postoperative complications at a postoperative MELD score greater than 13. Portal hypertension syndrome is an absolute contraindication for laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the open approach or early conversion being preferable.

In our study, laparoscopy was preferred in 75% of cases, with a relatively high conversion rate - 10%. However, open surgery in cirrhotic patients was associated with high morbidity rates (5-20%), even in this study a significant correlation was observed between the type of approach and postoperative complications. The main postoperative complications of open operations are hemorrhage, vascular decompensation with ascites and upper digestive hemorrhage, wound suppuration. Open cholecystectomy was considered a contraindication for this fragile group of patients. However, careful evaluation of risk factors and appropriate preoperative treatment may lead to the extension of these indications.

Laparoscopic surgery has indisputable advantages over the classical approach: better postoperative evolution, with minimal pain, early mobilization, faster resumption of oral nutrition and digestive transit, lower postoperative morbidity (hepatic failure is much less often), short convalescence with the avoidance of complications related (hemorrhage, hematomas and parietal suppurations, ascites infection, abscesses and eviscerations). There remain the problems of risk assessment and the technical difficulties of minimally invasive surgery for cirrhotic patients.

Conclusions

Patients with Child-Pugh A cirrhosis without portal hypertension have the same indication for elective cholecystectomy as non-cirrhotic ones, but with increased risks. Therefore, preoperative management should be adapted to each individual case.

Patients with Child-Pugh B cirrhosis or those with portal hypertension require preoperative evaluation and improvement of liver function.

For patients with Child-Pugh C cirrhosis, with limited life expectancy, surgical interventions should be avoided, seeking non-invasive alternative solutions.

Emergency surgery for acute cholecystitis and the open approach have the highest risk for adverse outcomes.

The retrospective character of the majority of studies and with a small number of patients taken into account, requires additional investigations in the future to outline some significant conclusions.

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